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How to Learn the Art of Management?

On 4-5 April 2023, as part of a series of regular professional, scientific events in the speciality “Management of Socio-Cultural Activities”, the Department of Fashion and Show Business of the Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts became the organiser of the VII All-Ukrainian Scientific and Methodological Seminar “Formation of a Modern Paradigm of Management Education in the Socio-Cultural Sphere”¹.

The scientific and methodological event brought together representatives of institutions of higher and pre-higher education that train cultural professionals – managers of socio-cultural activities – within the framework of educational activities in relevant educational and professional programmes at such universities as Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, Kyiv University of Culture, Kremenchuk Mykhailo Ostrohradskyi National University, National Academy of Culture and Arts Management, Sumy State University and in professional colleges: I. Ohienko Zhytomyr Professional College of Culture and Arts, Lviv Professional College of Culture and Arts, Tulchyn Professional College of Culture.

¹ Martynyshyn, Ya. (Head), & Khlystun, O., et al. (Eds.). (2023). *Formuvannia Suchasnoi Paradyhmy Menedzhment-Osvity u Sotsiokul'turnij Sferi [Formation of the Modern Paradigm of Management Education in the Socio-Cultural Sphere]. Zbirnyk Materialiv VII Vseukraïns'koho Naukovo-Metodychnoho Seminaru [Collection of Materials of the VII All-Ukrainian Scientific and Methodical Seminar]*. Kyiv: KNUKiM (in Ukr.).

Retrieved from https://drive.google.com/file/d/1eeCCeVraQPmHllcXjPPjnbMpZfR84D_5/view

The reports presented at the seminar by academic and pedagogical staff, master's students, and students of universities and colleges presented a comprehensive multi-level analysis of various aspects related to the training of modern professionals in the socio-cultural sphere – cultural managers. It covered a wide range of issues: awareness of new requirements and socio-cultural challenges to the professional activity of a manager in the era of globalisation; formation of new concepts and identification of the features of socio-cultural management; description of the key abilities of a modern manager required by the labour market; discussion of trends and transformation processes covering the management education system both in Ukraine and in the world; analysis of current problems of education for managers and pedagogical technologies for its development.

The event participants raised acute and controversial issues and reflected on the current vectors topics of development of a modern specialist in the socio-cultural sphere. In particular, professors of the Department of Fashion and Show Business of KNUKiM *Ya. Martynyshyn* and *O. Khlystun*, noting the use of competence-based, project-based, practice-oriented, and problem-oriented approaches in management education, stressed that it is almost impossible to identify stable laws in management as a practical science of a weak epistemological level. But, unlike other strong version sciences, management has temporary and unstable patterns. Therefore, “scientific methods of abstraction and formalisation should be used with great care; there are such metaphysical substances to which the scientific method cannot be applied at all (“fate”, “will”, “faith”, “vision”, etc.)”. Continuing this line of discussion, many scholars also noted the role of emotional resources management (“emotional management”) in improving business efficiency, which requires developed emotional intelligence (*Yu. Tymchenko*) and a focus on developing managers' abilities to implement the concept of “success-luck” associated with professional sense and intuition as abilities that allow cognising the irrational and are very important for the overall success of a manager (*Ye. Kovalenko*). The participants also noted that the formation of a strategic organisation of thinking (search for analogues, combining, reconstructing, and universal actions) in future managers deserves special attention (*O. Kostiuchenko, L. Butko*).

At the same time, in the current conditions of managerial training, scholars focus on value-based educational policy, which actualises the need to expand the range of civic participation in socio-cultural projects, progressive leadership, the introduction of a dual model of education as a practice-oriented model, as well as the transformation of the practice-oriented model of managerial education in martial law (*O. Kalantaievska, O. Krupa, A. Lebid, V. Opanasiuk, I. Parkhomenko, V. Shabunina, Yu. Shmehelska, T. Filina*).

The seminar proved that modern researchers of the system of training managers of socio-cultural activities are concerned with the peculiarities of implementing state policy (*D. Tytarenko*), planning and creation of cities within the framework of the introduction to the content of the discipline “Cultural Urbanism” which studies the development of urban systems and their interaction with city residents, which is interesting in the context of managers' activities in urban communities (*M. Proskurina*), as well as the role of a manager of socio-cultural activities in the context of developing a system of management of territorial united communities (*M. Kysil, Y. Tsiupka*).

The participants of the seminar were very interested in practical methods and applied practices of developing the qualities of modern managers: introduction of new pedagogical forms and methods into the educational process (*V. Maslak*), development of the culture of event technologies (*G. Hvozdkova, A. Huniak*), use of multimedia platforms to promote a personal brand and artistic product, storytelling, and blogging (*V. Datsun, M. Hladenko, K. Kravchenko, T. Povaliy, D. Solonina, A. Tkachenko, N. Khimchyk*), means of developing time management (*V. Prykhozhai*), case study approach in practical classes (*M. Bryl*), possibilities of using methods of non-verbal technologies of ocular (*T. Hryhorchuk*), recreational quests (*A. Moskalenko*) and development of programmes for the management of historical memory and military tourism, peculiarities of implementation of socio-cultural projects under martial law (*O. Bohaterenko, T. Tymofieieva, M. Tkachenko*), organisation of management activities in student self-government bodies (*S. Stokratna*).

Thus, the seminar participants concluded that the synthesis of theoretical and professional knowledge, practical skills, and abilities, together with the abilities and qualities of the individual, are the basic basis of the professional skills of a socio-cultural manager, which is necessary for the successful solution of various professional tasks in socio-cultural activities.

The abstracts of the reports of all the event participants were included in a scientific collection, which is available online on the library website of the Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts for free access.

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